

Myanmar Named Entity Recognition with Hidden Markov Model

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ABSTRACT

Named Entity Recognition is the process to detect Named Entities (NEs) in a file, document or from a corpus and to categorize them into certain Named entity classes like name of city, State, Country, organization, person, location, sport, river, quantity etc. This paper introduces the Named Entities Recognition (NER) for Myanmar language using Hidden Markov Model (HMM). The main idea behind the use of HMM language independent and we can apply this system for any language domain. The corpus used by our NER system is also not domain specific.

Keywords: Named Entity Recognition (NER), Natural Language processing (NLP), Hidden Markov Model (HMM)

I. INTRODUCTION

Named Entity Recognition is a subtask of Information extraction whose aim is to classify text from a document or corpus into some predefined categories like person name (PER), location name (LOC), organization name (ORG), month, date, time etc. And other to the text which is not named entities. NER has many applications in NLP. Some of the applications include machine translation, more accurate internet search engines, automatic indexing of documents, automatic question answering, information retrieval etc. An accurate NER system is needed for these applications. Most NER systems use a rule based approach or statistical machine learning approach or a Combination of these.

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A Rule-based NER system uses hand-written rules frame by linguist which are certain language dependent rules that help in the identification of Named Entities in a document. Rule based systems are usually best performing system but suffers some limitation such as language dependent, difficult to adapt changes.

II. RELATED WORK

There are a variety of techniques for NER. NER is classified two approaches:

A. Linguistic approach

The linguistic approach is the classical approach written by linguists to NER. It typically uses rules manually written by linguists. Though it requires a lot of work by domain experts, a NER system based on manual rules may provide very high accuracy. Rule based systems are lexicalized grammar, gazetteer lists, and list of trigger words. The main disadvantages of these rule based techniques are: they require huge experience and grammatical knowledge on the particular language or domain; the development is generally time-consuming and sometimes changes in the system may be hard to accommodate.

B. Machine learning based approach

The recent Machine learning (ML) techniques make use of a large amount of annotated data to acquire high level

language knowledge. ML based techniques facilitate the development of recognizers in a short time. Several ML techniques have been successfully used for the NER task. HMM is a ML approaches like Support Vector Machine (SVM), Condition Random Field (CRF), Maximum Entropy Markov Model (MEMM) are also used in developing NER systems.

III. OUR PROPOSED METHOD

A. HMM based NER

We are using Hidden Markov Model based machine learning approach. Named Entity Recognition in Myanmar Languages is a current topic of research. The HMM based NER system works in three phases. The first phase is referred to as „Annotation phase“ that produces tagged or annotated document from the given raw text, document or corpus. The second phase is referred to as „Training Phase“. In this phase, it computes the three parameters of HMM i.e. Start Probability, Emission Probability (B) and the Transition Probability (A). The last phase is the „TESTING Phase“. In this phase, user gives certain test sentences to the system, and based on the HMM parameters computed in the previous state, Viterbi algorithm computes the optimal state sequence for the given test sentence.

Fig. 3.1: Steps in NER using HMM

B. Step 1: Data Preparation

We need to convert the raw data into trainable form, so as to make it suitable to be used in the Hidden Markov model framework for all the languages. The training data may be collected from any source like from open source, tourism corpus or simply a plaintext file containing some sentences. So in order to make these file in trainable form we have to perform following steps:

Input: Raw text file

Output: Annotated Text (tagged text)

Algorithm

Step1: Separate each word in the sentence.

Step2: Tokenize the words.

Step3: Perform chunking if required.

Step5: Tag (Named Entity tag) the words by using your experience.

Step6: Now the corpus is in trainable form.

C. Step 2: HMM Parameter Estimation

Input: Annotated tagged corpus

Output: HMM parameters

Procedure:

Step1: Find states.

Step2: Calculate Start probability (π).

Step3: Calculate transition probability (A)

Step4: Calculate emission probability (B)

D. Procedure to find states

State is vector contains all the named entity tags candidate interested.

Input: Annotated text file

Output: State Vector

Algorithm:

For each tag in annotated text file

If it is already in state vector

Ignore it

Otherwise

Add to state vector

E. Procedure to find Start probability

Start probability is the probability that the sentence start with particular tag.

So start probabilities (π) =

$$\frac{\text{(Number of sentences start with particular tag)}}{\text{(Total number of sentences in corpus)}} \quad (1.1)$$

Input: Annotated Text file:

Output: Start Probability Vector

Algorithm:

For each starting tag

Find frequency of that tag as starting tag

Calculate π

F. Procedure to find Transition probability

If there is two pair of tags called T_i and T_j then transition probability is the probability of occurring of tag T_j after T_i .

So Transition Probability (A) =

$$\frac{\text{(Total number of sequences from } T_i \text{ to } T_j)}{\text{(Total number of } T_i)} \quad (1.2)$$

Input: annotated text file

Output: Transition Probability

Algorithm:

For each tag in states (T_i)

For each other tag in states (T_j)

If T_i not equal to T_j

Find frequency of tag sequence $T_i T_j$ i.e. T_j after T_i

Calculate $A = \text{frequency}(T_i T_j) / \text{frequency}(T_i)$

G. Procedure to find emission probability

Emission probability is the probability of assigning particular tag to the word in the corpus or document.

So emission probability (B) =

$$\frac{\text{(Total number of occurrence of word as a tag)}}{\text{(Total occurrence of that tag)}} \quad (1.3)$$

Input: Annotated Text file

Output: Emission Probability matrix

Algorithm:

For each unique word W_i in annotated corpus

Find frequency of word W_i as a particular tag T_i

Divide frequency by frequency of that tag T_i

H. Step 3: Testing

After calculating all these parameters we apply these parameters to Viterbi algorithm and testing sentences as an observation to find named entities. We used the training data 3000 sentences and testing data 150 sentences of Myanmar language.

IV. EXAMPLE

Consider these raw text containing 5 sentences of Myanmar language.

အနောက်ဖက်လွန်မင်းတရားကြီး/PER သည်/OTHER
 ၁၆၃၀/OTHER ခုနှစ်/OTHER တွင်/OTHER
 မင်းဆက်/OTHER သစ်/OTHER တစ်/OTHER
 ခု/OTHER ကို/OTHER အင်းဝ/LOC တွင်/OTHER
 ထူထောင်/OTHER ခဲ့/OTHER သည်/OTHER //sb

ဘုရားသခင်/OTHER သည်/OTHER မဟာမိတ်/PER
 အား/OTHER အမိန့်/OTHER ဒေသနာ/OTHER
 များ/OTHER ကို/OTHER ဟောကြား/OTHER
 ပို့သ/OTHER ရန်/OTHER စေလွှတ်/OTHER
 လိုက်/OTHER သည်/OTHER //sb

စန္ဒဂုတ္တမောရိယမင်း/PER သည်/OTHER ဂင်္ဂါ
 မြစ်ဝှမ်း/LOC မှ/OTHER တိုင်း/OTHER များ/OTHER
 ကို/OTHER ပါ/OTHER သိမ်းသွင်း/OTHER ပြီးလျှင်/
 OTHER ကျယ်ပြန့်/OTHER သော/OTHER မောရိယ
 နိုင်ငံတော်/LOC ကြီး/OTHER ကို/OTHER
 ထူထောင်/OTHER နိုင်/OTHER ခဲ့/OTHER
 သည်/OTHER //sb

ကြည်းတပ်/ OTHER ရေတပ်/OTHER နှင့်/OTHER
 လေတပ်/OTHER တို့/OTHER ကို/OTHER
 စုပေါင်း/OTHER ချ်/OTHER စင်္ကာပူတပ်မတော်/ORG
 ဟု/OTHER ခေါ်ဆို/OTHER ကြ/OTHER သည်/OTHER
 //sb

ဦးသန်း/PER သည်/OTHER ၁၉၅၇/OTHER ခုနှစ်/OTHER
 မှ/OTHER ၁၉၆၀/OTHER ခုနှစ်/OTHER အထိ/OTHER
 မြန်မာနိုင်ငံ/LOC ၏/OTHER ကုလသမဂ္ဂ/ORG
 အမြဲတမ်း/OTHER ကိုယ်စားလှယ်/OTHER
 အဖြစ်/OTHER သာမက/OTHER
 အယ်လ်ဂျီးရီးယားနိုင်ငံ/LOC ၏/OTHER
 လွတ်လပ်ရေး/OTHER စေ့စပ်/OTHER ဆွေးနွေး/OTHER
 မှု/OTHER များ/OTHER တွင်/OTHER လည်း/OTHER
 ပါဝင်/OTHER ခဲ့/OTHER သည်/OTHER //sb

PER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER
 OTHER OTHER LOC OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER

OTHER OTHER PER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER
 OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER

PER OTHER LOC OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER
 OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER LOC OTHER OTHER OTHER
 OTHER OTHER OTHER

OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER
 OTHER ORG OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER

PER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER
 LOC OTHER ORG OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER LOC OTHER
 OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER OTHER
 OTHER OTHER OTHER

Now we calculate all the parameters of HMM model. These are
States= { PER ,LOC, ORG, OTHER,}

Total Sentences = 5
 Total words for PER = 4
 Total words for LOC = 5
 Total words for ORG = 2
 Total words for OTHER= 77

TABLE.I START PROBABILITY(π)

PER	LOC	ORG	OTHER
3/5	0/5	0/5	2/5

TABLE.II TRANSACTION PROBABILITY(A)

	PER	LOC	ORG	OTHER
PER	0	0	0	4/4
LOC	0	0	0	5/5
ORG	0	0	0	2/2
OTHER	1/77	5/77	2/77	69/77

Emission Probability (B) =

Since in the emission probability we have to consider all the words in the file. But it's not possible to display all the words so we just gave the snapshot of first sentence of the file. Similarly we can find the emission probability of all the words.
 PER = 1/4
 LOC = 1/5
 ORG = 0/2
 OTHER = 13/77

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To evaluate the algorithm through accuracy, precision, recall and f-measure in table 2, there is a need to count true positives, false positive, true negative and false negatives in the result records [8] table1.

Precision: It is the fraction of the correct answers produced by the algorithm to the total answer produced. The formula for precision is:

$$\text{Precision(P)} = (\text{Corrected answers} / \text{answers produced}) \quad (1.4)$$

Recall: It is the fraction of the documents that are matching to the query mentioned and are successfully retrieved. Recall is calculated in the following manner:

$$\text{Recall (R)} = (\text{Corrected answers} / \text{total possible answers}) \quad (1.5)$$

F-Measure: It is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. The F-Measure is calculated as:

$$\text{F-Measure} = (2 * R * P) / (R + P) \quad (1.6)$$

$$\text{Precision} = TP / (TP + FP);$$

$$\text{Recall} = TP / (TP + FN);$$

$$\text{F-Measure} = 2 * \text{precision} * \text{recall} / (\text{precision} + \text{recall});$$

$$\text{accuracy} = (TP + TN) / \text{total-population(N)}$$

TABLE.III CONFUSION MATRIX FOR A BINARY CLASSIFIER

N = 3150	Postive	Negative	
Training	TP = 2620	TN = 380	3000
Testing	FP = 19	FN = 131	150
	2639	511	

TP = True Postive
 TN = True Negative
 FP = False Postive
 FN = False Negative

TABLE.IV MEASURE ON TEST DATA

Measures	Result
Accuracy	0.9523809523809523
Precision	0.9928003031451307
Recall	0.9523809523809523
F-Measure	0.9721706864564007

VI. CONCLUSION

Named Entity Recognition is a long-studied technology with a wide range of natural language applications. NER systems have been developed for resource-rich languages like English with very high accuracies. But construction of an NER system for a resource-poor language like Myanmar language is very challenging due to unavailability of proper resources. Myanmar is no concept of capitalization which is the indicator of proper names for some other languages like English. If we perform Named Entity Recognition in HMM and also provide the ways to improve the accuracy and the performance metrics.

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